

Special Issue on

Coronavirus

Christian Reflections and Responses

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Editorial: Courage, Consolation and Compassion in Times of Coronavirus

Pope Francis has been very close to those acutely suffering from Coronavirus and COVID-19. He has been offering prayers for deliverance from the deadly sickness. On March 27, 2020 at his “*Urbi et orbi*” (“to the City and to the World”) Blessing, he meditated on the calming of the storm from the Gospel of Mark (Mk 4:35-41).

On Monday, March 30, 2020, the Pope’s intention was “for the many people who are not succeeding in coping and remain in fear because of the pandemic.” Further, the “Easter People,” could not celebrate this joyful event.

UN Secretary General António Guterres has warned that the current coronavirus outbreak is the biggest challenge for the world since World War II. He said it could bring a recession “that probably has no parallel in the recent past”.

His warning comes amid dire predictions about the possible economic impact of measures imposed to fight the virus, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome CoronaVirus 2,” or SARS-CoV-2.

As of April 9, 2020, it has affected 15,11,104 and tragically 88,338 people over the whole world, with their dreams, stories, hopes and anxieties have died. In India, there are 5274 confirmed cases with 149 deaths. It is tragic. Painful.

In this context, we want to reflect on this tragic and painful topic from our Christian faith and paschal feast. The aim of these essays is not to sow panic or depression, but to evoke

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courage, hope and compassion. It must be acknowledged that these essays are not based on the latest scientific findings, for which we recommend the readers to use reliable scientific and medical sources. Sadly, there are so many myths and fake news promoted on this occasion.

Respecting the scientific development and hoping that a reliable vaccine may be soon discovered, these articles urge the Christian faithful to be open to God’s grace and to trust in Him fully, since He is our only Hope.

The articles in this volume are roughly divided into the seven last words of Jesus, reflecting the present moment of Paschal Mystery. The first eight article reflect on the quarantine, getting in touch with oneself and related themes. Though it is truly challenging task for many families, the lockdown invites us to be in touch with our innermost self and to recall spiritually the assurance of Jesus: “Truly, I say to you, today you will be with me in Paradise” (Lk 23:43)

The next set of articles look on the scientific basis of coronavirus and the harm that we have done to mother earth. While acknowledging the miracle that science and technology have been for humanity, we need to acknowledge that we misuse this power to exploit the earth. In this section, we can listen to the consoling words of Jesus: “Father, forgive them, for they know not what they do.” (Lk 23:34). This is followed by four articles connected with plague and epidemic in the history of humanity. The millions of people who have died in numerous plagues should remind us of Jesus entrusting all these dead and suffering people to Mary, just as he entrusted John to her. So, we listen to Jesus, “Woman, behold, your son” (Jn 19:26).

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In the fourth section, we deal with the numerous lessons we can learn from this tragic corona experience. Hopefully these lessons will change our life-style and lead us different ways of fulfilling our expectations. Hopefully we shall learn to live as brothers and sisters. This reminds us of Jesus' words: "I thirst" (Jn 19: 28). The next section deal with God and how we experience God in these agonising moments. In spite of our unbelief, struggle and pessimism, we do find courage to surrender ourselves to this God, who we believe loves us unconditionally. Thus, we can make Jesus' prayer our own: "Father, into your hands I commit my spirit!" (Lk 23:46).

Still there is no escape from fear, angst and a sense of rejection. Even when we look a the crucified Lord, we feel abandoned and helpless. Hence, we make our own the anguish of Jesus: "My God, my God, why have you forsaken me?" (Mt 17:46).

In the concluding section with faith and trust we say it is finished or fulfilled, in ways not fully known to us. We try to derive hope and discern the will of God in all these terrible experiences of suffering, angst, abandonment and loss. We want to acknowledge that though we feel helpless, we are not hopeless, since HE walks with us! "It is accomplished." (Jn 19:30).

The article in this volume urges the readers to take the Coronavirus threat seriously, but not get into panic or depression. It urges caution and care, but not dread, since we can always trust in the Risen Lord, who alone is our hope.

May this Pascal Feast bring us abundance of joy and hope based on the courage, consolation that we draw from our faith! May our living faith make us truly compassionate, especially to those affected by COVID-19. Our prayers for all of you.

The Editor

Home Quarantine as Home-Coming

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Home quarantine as a precaution to protect oneself from deadly pandemic covid-19 is indeed a unique opportunity for humans to home-coming. The metaphor 'Home-Coming' can be understood, both literally and symbolically. Home-coming literally means that we humans have gone too far in different crossroads in search of wealth that is transitory, social recognition that is fleeting, and the pleasures of the world that are momentary. Symbolically, home-coming could be understood as the need humans feel to return to their original home, their original self or return to the 'inner' self. The reason behind this is our obsession with 'activism,' always seeking ways and means solely in the direction of profit motive. But this overemphasis on outward actions can lead to adverse side-effects. What we need today is a good blend between these two extreme poles, one complementing the other. Most of the spiritual Gurus time and again have warned that authentic spirituality ought to deepen our journey in both directions. Henry Nouwen has rightly pointed out that: "Solitude is the furnace of transformation. Without solitude we remain victims of our society and continue to be entangled in the illusions of the false self." The sudden eruption of covid-19 sweeping the entire world, irrespective of all human made boundaries like developed or underdeveloped, rich or poor, without caste, creed and religion has taught us many hard lessons. No corner of the world is untouched and no life is unaffected by this pandemic.